

CHATGPT

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Abstract:- According to OpenAI, ChatGPT is an artificial intelligence trained to assist various of tasks, which means that to use ChatGPT, you present your query or question to the tool by typing through a chat box, the tool then processes your request and answers you based on the information that it has available.

“Nobody phrases it this way, but I think that artificial intelligence is almost a humanities discipline. It’s really an attempt to understand human intelligence and human cognition.”

-Sebastian Thrun

I. INTRODUCTION

ChatGPT is an AI chatbot that has been a trending topic since it was launched by OpenAI late 2022, It is surprising how this tool is capable to do, from holding a conversation to writing an entire search paper. It’s also capable to make a brand logo, composing messages and so much more.

II. TECHNICAL BACKGROUND

ChatGPT works through its Generative Pre-trained Transformer, which uses specialized algorithms to find patterns within data sequences. ChatGPT uses the GPT-3 language model, a neural network machine learning model and the third generation of Generative Pre-trained Transformer.

ChatGPT uses deep learning to produce humanlike text through transformer neural networks, which predicts text, including words, sentences and paragraphs based on it’s training data.

ChatGPT trained with online text to learn human language where human trainers provide conversations and rank the responses by upvoting or downvoting them which helps in determining the best answers.

III. CHATGPT USAGES

People use ChatGPT for different reasons, including:

- Compose Music.
- Answer different questions.
- Draft emails.
- Design presentations.
- Write articles.

IV. PROS & CONS

ChatGPT similar to any other provided services has various advantages and disadvantages.

A. Advantages Include

- Provide answers for complicated questions.
- Free usage.
- User-friendly.
- Adaptive learning.

B. Disadvantages Include

- Data accuracy.
- Limited knowledge resources.
- Lack of quality control.
- -Data Privacy.
- -Replace Human beings’ jobs with machines.

V. CONCLUSION

As of today, ChatGPT is a great service that can make our lives easy by performing multiple tasks. Yet, it is a new introduced service that has many aspects.

Some scientists predict that AI will achieve human-level intelligence, while others says it will likely lead to the loss of jobs, resulting in a rise in poverty

What we know that It will remain growing as long as human beings communicate with it and utilize it which makes it difficult to measure the real impact of such tool on our societies, families and jobs.

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